

Certificate

This is to certify that

CBM INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY

1110 Nuuanu Ave, PMB 1136, Honolulu, HI 96817, USA

has been found in Compliance with requirements of

Quality Management System

ISO 9001:2015

for the following scope:

INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH SERVICES.

Certificate No. : 9765/QMS/0922

Issue Date : 19-September-2022

Expiry Date : 18-September-2025

To check this certificate status visit:

["http://uasl.uk.com/certifiedorganization.html"](http://uasl.uk.com/certifiedorganization.html)

Authorised Signature

International Accurate Certification

60 Mill Mead Business Centre,
Mill Mead Road, London N17 9QU, United Kingdom
www.iacert.com & info@iacert.com

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Certified organization

CERTIFICATE NO.	ORG. NAME	ADDRESS	SCOPE	STANDARD	CAB NAME	STATUS
9765/QMS/0922	CBM INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY	MIG-9, NK NAGAR, BERHAMPUR CIRCLE-1, ODISHA-760002. INDIA	INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH SERVICES.	ISO 9001:2015	International Accurate Certification	valid

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9765/QMS/0922

Please Enter Company Name (At Least First 3 Characters)

CBM

Certificate 9765/QMS/0922 Details

Name	Address	Scope	Standard	Issue Date	Valid Upto
CBM INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY	MIG-9, NK NAGAR, BERHAMPUR CIRCLE-1, ODISHA-760002, INDIA	INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH SERVICES.	ISO 9001:2015	19-Sep-2022	18-Sep-2025

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